

Exploratory Analysis and Determinants of the Digital Divide: The Case of Tunisia

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ABSTRACT: The growing use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) is evolving at a rapid pace and leading to major changes in both developed and developing countries. However, while ICTs are seen as a vector of progress and access to new opportunities and for many, the use of these technologies is synonymous with the acceleration of digital capabilities, they can also amplify regional disparities and widen the gap between regions. This article aims to analyze and identify the various models of adoption behaviors of ICTs within Tunisian districts. The descriptive and exploratory analysis revealed significant regional disparities in ICT adoption rates, with a distinct "gap" between inland and coastal regions. Thus, the findings suggest that ICT adoption rates exhibit non-neutral spatial distribution patterns and show that taking into account the spatial dimension of the data makes it possible to assess the extent to which the results usually observed can be modified. A spatial autoregressive model shows that different socio-economic and geographical factors intervene in explaining the disparities in ICT acquisition rates in Tunisian districts.

KEYWORDS: ICTs, Digital divide, Regional development, Spatial econometrics, Tunisia.

JEL Classification: O1, O55, C21, R23

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid diffusion of ICTs has accelerated rapidly and caused a dramatic transformation of the world into an information society (Bahrini and Qaffas, 2019, Anel and al., 2021). These technologies have become the main driver of improvements in the internal processes, communication, products and services, and the business model (Van Veldhoven & Vanthienen, 2021, Qadikolaie and al., 2022). Therefore, the widespread use of these technologies has made access to technology usage skills, and the quality of technology services increasingly important (Sezgin and Firat, 2024). Consequently, ICT diffusion has attracted the interest of economists, managers and public decision-makers as it is crucial to comprehend their effects in the socio-economic sphere as well as at the regional level with many research studies having explored its impact on economic growth (Kadi, 2007).

The digitalization revolution—the rapid development of mobile Internet, the Internet of things, cloud computing, artificial intelligence, and other digital technologies—is ever more integrated into the economy and society and is transforming the way we live, work, and communicate (Morrar and al., 2017; Autio and al., 2021). This digital revolution has become a tangible reality across all sectors of the economy, unleashing a wave of rapid technological advances (Bourreau and Pénard, 2016; Chappell, 2016; Tremblay and Yagoubi, 2018). Generally, there is a consensus that ICTs constitute the driving force behind a new industrial revolution impacting economic growth and social welfare (Rallet and Rochelandet, 2004). Thus, the latter half of the twentieth century was characterized by industries investing heavily in ICTs to become nationally and globally competitive (Shaaba Saba, 2023). Indeed, the COVID-19 pandemic has shown how important the level of development ICT, digital technologies, and access to the network is, all over the world (Vasa and al., 2023).

ICTs play a significant role in development processes and economic growth, and they are progressively finding their place in all aspects of society, expected to yield productivity improvements, irrespective of the economic, institutional, and cultural environment in which they are deployed. Thus, the implementation of new territorial management approaches based on ICTs seems essential for regional development and the enhancement of regions is viewed as both a challenge and a priority objective for states (Benkaraache and al., 2016). Recent research indicate that ICTs have not only shown substantial growth as an innovative technology industry sector but also possesses a strong capability to contribute to the advancement of other sectors (Bourquin, 2017; Ukwuoma, 2019). In this regard, due to their transformative potential, these technologies can address development needs by serving as a driver for technological progress and a mechanism for establishing and consolidating a position within the international competition (Belattaf and Alilat, 2021).

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On the other hand, the emergence of ICTs and the reduction of digital divides are frequently emphasized as key elements of the digital economy. They have become crucial factors influencing economic and social activities in both developed and emerging countries (Kumar, 2008; Al Malkawi and al., 2011; Kossay, 2013). While regional economic and digital inequalities have been examined from various perspectives, significant knowledge gaps remain regarding these issues themselves and the spatially relevant economic impacts of digitalization (Haimeng and al., 2024). In this sense, the relationship between ICTs, spatial organization, and territorial planning is complex. Indeed, the impact of ICTs is the subject of two contradictory visions. ICTs are viewed as tools to reduce distance and promote a more uniform world. The removal of physical barriers has paved the way for extensive communication. For this reason, by influencing the concept of proximity, these technologies enable a dispersion of activities geographically, typically concentrated in urban clusters and major cities, leading to a rebalancing of regions and the opportunity to stimulate economic growth in overlooked or rural areas. They offer substantial potential in addressing social and economic inequalities. On the other hand, ICTs can exacerbate regional disparities, broaden the rural-urban gap, potentially reinforcing existing inequalities (Rallet and Rochelandet, 2004, Chusnul and al., 2021). This gap is not just the unavailability of information and communication technology but also a gap in usage skills and the actual usage of digital technologies (Salemin et al., 2017).

The structure of the article is as follows: Section 2 first gives an overview of the role of ICTs in regional development and secondly the relationship between the digital divide and regional imbalances. Section 3 analyses the level of diffusion of ICTs in the Tunisian economy, while Section 4 will study the disparities and determinants of the diffusion of ICTs in the 264 Tunisian districts according to the latest census of 2014.

2. ICTS, ECONOMIC GROWTH AND DIGITAL DIVIDE

The worldwide rapid progress of ICTs in the last three decades has attracted increasing attention by many economists and researchers who have focused on studying the impact of ICT diffusion on the economic growth of developed and developing countries (Rodriguez, 2013, Bahrini and Qaffas, 2019). Also, with the rapid development of big data, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence, digital technologies have been applied in a much wider and deeper manner (Haimeng and al., 2024). This has spurred extensive economic literature, questioning ICT's role in economic growth, epitomized by the Solow's famous "productivity paradox" remark in 1987, "You can see computers everywhere except in productivity statistics" (Cohen and Debonneui, 1998). This remark has spurred decades of research and debate on the role that ICTs play on productivity (Polák, 2014).

Recent studies have shed light on ICT impact on economic growth, productivity, employment, organizational efficiency, performance, competitiveness, and human capital development (Kossay, 2013), highlighting a significant positive correlation between ICTs and economic growth. Recently, Vu and al. (2020) surveyed the literature to probe the role that ICTs plays in driving economic growth. The findings show a positive link with growth, despite this subject still being an open discourse among researchers (Shaaba and Ngepah, 2022). However, identifying and examining the intellectual contributions that have accumulated knowledge on regional phenomena and territorial development over time is a complex task (Lafontaine, 2012). These theories posit that ICTs serve as a capital input in economic supply, enhancing the production process by increasing capital and driving technological progress (Bahrini and Qaffas, 2019). Nevertheless, efficient telecommunications infrastructure provision yields direct benefits through lower transaction costs and improved market information, while also generating indirect benefits through enhanced information dissemination (Pradhan et al., 2014). So, these technologies not only represent a significant technological innovation but also facilitate the creation of high-value applications, streamline production processes, and reduce transaction and transportation costs (Czernich et al., 2011). Consequently, ICT investment contributes to increased human capital, improved efficiency, rapid technological advancements in ICT goods and services production, and accelerated growth in the ICT sector (Keček et al., 2016).

However, although the advancement of technology provides numerous opportunities to boost economic growth and development, equal distribution may not be guaranteed (Chusnul and al., 2021). Access to technology, technology usage skills, and Internet service quality create gaps between different segments of society all around the world and they can also serve as accelerators or catalysts for inequalities (Coron and Gilbert, 2019; Sezgin and Firat, 2024). Today, ICTs energize some and worry others and this surge in ICT adoption has also led to digital disparities, commonly known as the digital divide. Various studies indicate that the digital divide is very present especially in underdeveloped and developing countries (Sezgin and Firat, 2024).

The concept of digital divide¹ dates to the early 1990s with the distinction between the "information haves" and the "information have-nots" as identified in OECD reports (Rallet and Rochelandet, 2004). Originating in the United States, the term

¹ We can refer to the OECD (2001) definition of the "digital divide" as the gap between people and places of different socio-economic levels in terms of accessing information and communication technologies (ICTs) and using the Internet for various activities.

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emerged to address disparities in ICT use and access among various social groups. Furthermore, studies have also examined regional disparities within OECD countries due to Europe's slower ICT investment and diffusion. Indeed, while extensively studied, the topic remains complex due to its vague and broad nature, touching on different aspects of economic digitalization and the diffusion of information and communication technologies (Ben Youssef, 2014). The digital divide is not only determined by access to technology but also by the ability to effectively use the technology and encompasses dimensions such as technology ownership, technology use, Internet access, and socioeconomic level (Bagchi, 2005; Sezgin and Firat, 2024). The access and use of these technologies are unequal, with not everyone utilizing them to the same degree, possessing them, or accessing specific digital services. In this sense, the disparity in access to or utilization of ICT devices, as measured by the number of telephone lines per person, Internet users, or mobile phone users, deepens the gap between emerging and developing nations, particularly when new aspects of technology arise (Adam et al., 2021). In this regard, cases of lack of access to online resources for minorities, the elderly, low-income people, people with low levels of education, and people with disabilities have been identified (Qadikolaei and al., 2022).

Past studies evaluating the effect of ICT development on regional economies have been inconclusive on whether it will further aggravate or alleviate inequality (Chusul and al., 2021). ICTs contribute more to the urbanization of the territory than they hinder it. Economic activities exhibit a trend towards spatial polarization, leading to the concentration of telecommunications and Internet networks in the most densely populated and profitable areas (Theys and al., 2005). In this sense, the digital divide is conditioned by the necessary equipment and infrastructure for the diffusion and use of ICTs, as well as the actual practices and performance associated with these technologies (Chalita, 2012; Okunola and al., 2017). This disparity is not only due to access to technical and telecommunication infrastructure, but also to social factors concerning individuals and households. These factors encompass socio-demographic variables such as income levels, gender, race, age, household composition, employment status and more.

Measuring the digital divide involves quantitative studies and indices aimed at identifying relevant indicators of digital inequality (Wijers, 2010). So, it is a complex task to determine whether the digital divide merely delays diffusion or signifies structural inequalities that need addressing (Chalita, 2012). While research confirms the existence of a divide, the extent and evolution vary depending on the methodology used (Brandtzaeg and al., 2011). In this, sense, several studies have attempted to measure the digital divide and explore its multidimensional nature using indicators, thus capturing its complexity. Early attempts utilized different metrics to quantify digital disparity, such as the number of telephone lines per person, mobile phone ownership in a population, and broadband adoption (Kyriakidou and al., 2011; Aissaoui and Ben Hassen, 2016). Van Dijk (2017) evaluated ICT access through measures like computer use, internet use, broadband availability, usage duration and internet costs. Indeed, the digital disparity index proposed by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) considers factors such as the number of internet users, computers, mobile phone subscribers, internet bandwidth and broadband subscribers per 100 residents (Zhouying and al., 2019). Studies on inequalities distinguish between the "first-level digital divide" focusing on ICT access inequalities, and the "second-level digital divide" which addresses disparities in ICT usage (Leroy, 2020).

3. THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN TUNISIA

Due to its advantageous geographical position, Tunisia is an attractive investment destination in the digital sector, with the potential to serve as a central nexus connecting Europe, Africa, and the Middle East². The country is committed to advancing ICTs to modernize economic sectors, boost company competitiveness, and drive growth within the ICT industry, which plays a vital role in creating wealth and high-value jobs (Kamoun and al., 2010). It was one of the first countries in the Africa and Middle East region to establish and implement an ICT strategy, boasting a robust ICT infrastructure and a steadily increasing Internet penetration rate (Kossay, 2013)³. It leads the way in Africa with its advanced infrastructure, dedicated to use ICTs to transform various economic sectors, improve business performance and promote competitiveness. Simultaneously, the country is focused on bolstering the ICT sector as an independent economic force that promotes wealth creation and high value-added jobs. The government's efforts to bridge the digital divide between urban and rural areas include establishing infrastructure and implementing tax reduction programs. These efforts are instrumental in the industrial modernization drive, empowering companies to upgrade their operations in an increasingly competitive and globalized knowledge economy (Ben Khalifa, 2018).

Since the era of digital transformation, Tunisia has prioritized fostering a digital culture and utilization across administrations, productive sectors and the overall population. It has committed to various digital aspects that impact economic activities in general and the knowledge economy in particular (Nasri and al., 2020). The ICT sector, especially software, services and multimedia industry, has become a primary focus of Tunisia's development strategy (Jankari, 2014). A World Summit on the Information Society in Tunisia highlighted ICTs as a crucial tool for development, directly impacting poverty reduction,

² <https://www.francophoniedjerba2022.tn/fr/la-tunisie-numerique>.

³In 2015, Tunisia was among the most developed African countries in terms of ICT (5th rank according to the NRI index of the World Economic Forum – Network Readiness Index).

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innovation, promotion and economic growth. Tunisian digital sector shows promise, with export potential and acknowledged expertise in the global market⁴. The evolution of territorial development concepts in Tunisia reflects substantial transformations over time, in response to new economic, social, and environmental challenges, as well as the recent "revolution". Consequently, effective territorial development requires a precise strategy supported by diverse management practices and tools focused on communication, information transmission, knowledge capitalization and distribution (Ben Slymen, 2014).

Internationally, Tunisia has improved its ranking in certain global indices. It was placed 70th in the International Communication Union (ITU) Index relating to global development in the field of ICT in 2022 out of 193 countries⁵. This progress has led government entities to create a supportive regulatory framework and incentives to drive its development further (Kossay, 2013). Concerning human resources, the Tunisian government has consistently invested in enhancing skilling, allocating nearly 7% of the state budget to education. This initiative has increased the number of students specializing in ICT to over 13% of the total student population in the public sector (with most public and private institutions offering ICT training in faculties or engineering schools). According to the National Institute of Statistics, the ICT sector contributes 4.3% to GDP, 2.9% to investments, and employs 113,000 individuals as of 2022. Significantly, this sector serves as a catalyst for highly skilled professionals, fosters an environment that supports the software industry (such as technopoles, business incubators, etc.), and benefits from legislation that encourages entrepreneurship and innovation, notably through programs like Startup Tunisia⁶.

4. SPATIAL INEQUALITY AND DIGITAL DIVIDE IN TUNISIAN DISTRICTS

a. Exploratory spatial analysis

To evaluate variations in Internet usage rates, ownership of computers and mobile phones, we use data from the last General Population and Housing Census (2014), across 264 Tunisian districts. Indeed, the average Internet usage rate was 23.243%. So, the average of the ten highest rates stands at 65.088%, while the average of the ten lowest rates is 1.899%. This disparity not only underscores the numerical contrast but also accentuates the significance of the findings presented in the graphical analysis. Figure 1 (map 1) and the appendix show that the Internet usage rate varies considerably across the districts. Indeed, the country's coastal districts have better rates than the interior districts, which reinforces the center-periphery duality already observed. In this sense, while national data indicates Tunisia has made advancements in ICTs in recent years, significant disparities exist among individuals proficient in and possessing these technologies. As industrialization and urbanization accelerated, the gap between the east and west progressively widened. The eastern coastal regions were given priority and development support at the start of the reform. However, note that alleviating regional inequality has long been a priority for the Tunisian governments. They had enacted strategic plans since 1980 for the development of the western region, the revitalization of old industrial bases in the northeast, and the promotion of the central region, all to achieve balanced regional development and reduce regional inequalities. However, despite these considerable efforts and proactive policies, the country continues to face substantial inequalities in digital technologies. The search for explanations leads to reflections on the processes of diffusion and on the relationships of the facts of the present with characters deeply rooted in time.

Likewise, the lowest values of computer acquisition were recorded in western governorates like Kairouan, Kasserine, Jendouba and Zaghuan (map 2, figure 1 and appendix). In contrast, the data indicates that most districts in coastal governorates exhibit higher levels of computer use. The highest values were reported in Ariana, Ben Arous and Sousse. Gouvernorates. Note that the average of the ten highest rates is 69.277%, significantly higher than the average of the ten lowest rates (3.832%).

Concerning mobile phones, the average acquisition rate was 96.68%. 107 districts had rates below the national average. Map 3 (figure 1) and appendix shows that the lowest values are mainly in interior districts, while the highest rates are in coastal districts, similar to Internet and computer usage. The lowest values are recorded in the governorates of Kairouan, Jendouba, Kasserine, Sidi Bouzid, Siliana, Beja and Nabeul. On the other hand, the highest mobile phone acquisition rates are recorded in the governorates of Tunis, Ariana, Ben Arous, Sousse and Tataouine. As a result, the average of the ten lowest (highest) rates is 90.96% (99.33%). As a result, the difference is relatively small compared to Internet and computer. This is due to the affordability of mobile phones, making them accessible to everyone and transforming them from luxury items to necessities.

⁴ <https://www.francophoniedjerba2022.tn/fr/la-tunisie-numerique>.

⁵ <https://www.webdesign.tn/les-derniers-chiffres-du-secteur-des-tics-en-tunisie/>

⁶ <https://www.francophoniedjerba2022.tn/fr/la-tunisie-numerique>.

Figure 1: Internet, computer and mobile phone acquisition rates

Note that despite the observed regional disparities, inspection of the three maps (fig 1) reveals spatial clustering of low values in inland regions and high values in coastal regions. This is why it seemed justified to question the different forms of interdependencies in terms of ICTs within Tunisian districts. Technically, geographic proximity is the basic material for defining the patterns of interdependence between each pair of observations and measures of contiguity or distance are the most common. For this reason, we use the spatial weight matrix. The general form is defined by:

$$w_{ij}^{(sd)} = \frac{w_{ij}(k)}{\sum_j w_{ij}(k)} \text{ avec } w_{ij}(k) \text{ tels que } \begin{cases} w_{ij}(k) = 0 & \text{si } i = j \\ w_{ij}(k) = 1 & \text{si } d_{ij} < d_i(k) \\ w_{ij}(k) = 0 & \text{si } d_{ij} > d_i(k) \end{cases}$$

where $d_i(k)$ is the threshold distance defined for each district. It is the smallest distance between districts and such that the district has exactly k neighboring districts. To measure global spatial autocorrelation, the the Moran index is most commonly used. It is defined by:

$$I_M = \frac{N \sum_i \sum_j w_{ij} (x_i - \bar{x})(x_j - \bar{x})}{K \sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2}$$

Where x_i denotes the value of the ICT acquisition rate in the district i , N is the number of districts within the Tunisian space ($N=264$) and K is the sum of the interaction coefficients.

Based on the inverse distances matrix, the distribution of ICT acquisition rates in Tunisian districts shows a strong positive spatial autocorrelation (table1): the Moran's I statistic is indeed significantly positive. This means that there is an overall spatial trend towards the geographical clustering of similar ICT acquisition rates in the Tunisian space. So, districts characterized by similar levels tend to be located close to each other.

Table 1: Moran's statistics (Global spatial autocorrelation)

	I-Moran	St-Deviation	Std-Value	Critical-Pr
Internet	0.244	0.017	14.509	0.0001
Computer	0.343	0.027	14.166	0.0001
Mobile	0.409	0.018	22.880	0.0001

It has also been found that global analysis can sometimes hide spatial particularities while local analysis seeks to highlight them to reveal local associations and atypical data, and can sometimes contradict the results of global analysis. It consists of calculating local indices of spatial association derived from global indices or replacing the neighborhood matrix with the vector or line that corresponds to the regional unit, among which we cite the Moran Scatterplot and the LISA (Local Indicators of Spatial Association).

Figure (2) and table (2) reveal that 71.97% of districts exhibit a spatial association with similar values for the Internet use rate, 73.11% for computer and 79.17% for mobile phone. Specifically, 32.95% for the Internet (respectively 35.99% for computer

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and 50.38% for mobile phone) are clustered in the HH⁷ quadrant, while 39.02% (respectively 37.12% and 28.79%) are grouped in the LL quadrant. Conversely, 28.03% (respectively 26.89% and 20.83%) of these districts demonstrate a spatial association with dissimilar values. Among them, 12.12% (respectively 12.12% and 5.68%) are situated in the HL quadrant, and 15.91% (respectively 14.77% and 15.68%) are concentrated in the LH quadrant, where districts exhibit lower levels of digitization compared to their neighbors. It's noteworthy that a very slight difference is recorded when other spatial weight matrices were used, but the spatial concentration of similar values, particularly in the HH and LL quadrants, persists regardless of the spatial weight matrix used.

The abscissa shows the standardized value Z of the study variable (TICs) and the ordinate shows the spatially standardized value WZ .

Figure 2: Moran Scatterplot.

Table 2: Moran Scatterplot (Local spatial autocorrelation)

	Quadrant HH	Quadrant HL	Quadrant LH	Quadrant LL
Internet	87 (32.95%)	32 (12.12%)	42 (15.91%)	103 (39.02%)
Computer	95 (35.99%)	32 (12.12%)	39 (14.77%)	98 (37.12%)
Mobile	133 (50.38%)	15 (5.68%)	40 (15.15%)	76 (28.79%)

On the other hand, a local analysis based on LISA statistics allows us to distinguish whether the geographical groupings of districts are rather characterized by high or low values of the ICT acquisition. More precisely, the local version of Moran's I is calculated as follows:

$$LISA_i = \frac{(x_i - \bar{x})}{G} \sum_{j \text{ voisin}(i)} w_{ij} (x_j - \bar{x})^2 \text{ where } G = \sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2 / N$$

where x_i denotes the value of the variable for district i , N is the number of observations ($N = 264$).

Regarding Internet usage, table (3) reveals two distinct local patterns of positively significant spatial concentration, situated in the HH and LL quadrants, with percentages of 66.66% (58 out of 87 districts) and 67% (69 out of 103 districts) respectively. The percentage of significant negative clusters is 50% in the HF quadrant and 64.28% in the LH quadrant. Concerning computer usage, notable significant spatial concentrations are observed across the HH (68.42%), LL (71.42%) and LH (71.8%) quadrants. Conversely, for mobile phone data, the highest percentage is noted in the HL quadrant (80%), where a district with a high mobile phone acquisition rate is surrounded by districts with moderately low rates. Therefore, the bipolarization of the Tunisian territory is also strong since the significant clusters of either LL or HH types always represent at least 65% of the positive spatial autocorrelation. In this sense, spatial effects characterize neighborhood variables and the hypothesis that districts are isolated from other neighborhoods must be abandoned. So, within Tunisian districts, there is an overall trend towards the spatial concentration of similar characteristics with strongly marked polarization patterns: we are faced with both forms of spatial autocorrelation (cluster formation) and spatial heterogeneity (different polarizations of the HH or LL type).

⁷ The HH quadrant includes districts that have high ICT values surrounded by districts that also have high values. The LL quadrant translates the districts having low values surrounded by districts also having low values. The HL quadrant groups districts with high values surrounded by districts with low values. Finally, the LH quadrant contains districts with low values surrounded by districts with high values.

Table 3: LISA statistics of significance of spatial associations

	LISA-HH	LISA-HL	LISA-LH	LISA-LL
Internet	58 (66.66%)	16 (50%)	27 (64.28%)	69 (67%)
Computer	65 (68.42%)	12 (37.5%)	28 (71.8%)	70 (71.42%)
Mobile	100 (75.18%)	12(80%)	20 (50%)	59 (77.63%)

b. Determinants of digital divide in Tunisian districts

This section aims to clarify the socioeconomic factors contributing to the observed disparities and digital divide across Tunisian districts. The variables being studied are INT, CP and MB, representing Internet, computer and mobile phone acquisition rates, respectively. However, due to limited statistical data at the geographical level of analysis, five potential explanatory variables have been identified: urbanization rate (URB), unemployment rate (UNM), proportion of households with television (TV), percentage of households with individuals aged 15-40 (HSH), and enrollment rate in higher education (UNV). The model is as follows:

$$\begin{cases} ICT = \alpha S + \beta_1 URB + \beta_2 UNEM + \beta_3 TV + \beta_4 HSH_{15-40} + \beta_5 UNV + \varepsilon \\ \varepsilon \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

With S a unit vector and ε is the error vector with the usual properties of the standard linear regression model. Using the spatial weight matrix, table (4) indicates a significant Moran test value applied to the error terms (IM-Err). This result partially explains the Jarque-Bera (JB) et Breusch-Pagan (BP) statistic's magnitude, especially for the computer and the mobile phone. Consequently, the estimates derived from model (1) are biased and the variance-covariance matrix is not efficient, necessitating the exploration of alternative methods and models.

Table 4: Estimation results from classical models

Estimation	INT			Tests	INT		
	INT	CP	MB		INT	CP	MB
$\hat{\alpha}$	33.842 (0.046) *	6.853 (0.230)	10.124 (0.542)	JB	1215.552 (0.064)**	1765.663 (0.000)***	1523.124 (0.000)***
$\hat{\beta}_1$	0.885 (0.000)***	0.256 (0.018)**	0.152 (0.028)**	BP	113.223 (0.066)*	578.584 (0.000)***	495.125 (0.000)***
$\hat{\beta}_2$	-0.355 (0.000)***	-0.168 (0.114)	-0.125 (0.315)	KB	13.052 (0.070)*	73.168 (0.000)***	66.451 (0.000)***
$\hat{\beta}_3$	0.376 (0.059)*	0.698 (0.034)**	0.452 (0.123)	WH	68.993 (0.000)***	119.235 (0.000)***	89.254 (0.000)***
$\hat{\beta}_4$	0.435 (0.000)***	0.175 (0.094)*	0.257 (0.024)**	I_M	0.166 (0.000)***	0.167 (0.000)***	0.145 (0.000)***
$\hat{\beta}_5$	0.666 (0.011)**	0.1292 (0.034)**	0.114 (0.105)	LM-Lag	15,366 (0.002)***	16.546 (0.001)***	17.145 (0.000)***
R^2	0.738	07.69	0.684	RLM-Lag	10.597 (0.039)**	11,287 (0.056)*	10.451 (0.044)**
LogL	-667.524	-444.088	-554.088	LM-Err	12,600 (0.009)***	12.706 (0.008)***	11.124 (0.055)*
AIC	1351.05	904.176	1050.135	RLM-Err	7.831 (0.065)*	7.447 (0.084)*	7.748 (0.054)*
SC	1377.67	930.799	1030.854				

Notes: LogL denotes the value of the log likelihood function. AIC is Akaike's information criterion. SC is the Schwarz information criterion. JB is the Jarque-Bera residual normality test. BP, KB and WH are Breusch-Pagan's, Koenker-Bassett's and White's heteroscedasticity tests of the error terms respectively. IM-Err is Moran's test. LM-Lag and RLM-LAG refer respectively to the Lagrange multiplier test applied to the spatially endogenous variable and its robust version. LM-Err is the Lagrange multiplier test applied to the error terms and RLM-Err designates its robust version. Critical values are in parentheses. ***: significant at 1%, **: significant at 5%, *: significant at 10%.

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Spatial econometrics models are needed to justify, through their lessons in the analysis of spatial disparities, why geography should be taken into consideration in the modeling of georeferenced data. The two usual forms of spatial dependence are modeled using spatial autoregressive variables applied to the endogenous variable (SAR model: spatial autoregressive) or to the error term (SEM Spatial Error Model). According to table 4, the spatial lag model is identified as the most appropriate specification based on the Lagrange Multiplier test and its robust version and suggest a more appropriate correction by estimating SAR model rather than by estimating a SEM model. Therefore, the integration of accessibility, neighborhood and geographic variables into the initial model are sufficient to capture spatial effects. With the SAR model, the explanation is centered on the existence of geographic spillover. This model is presented as follow:

$$\begin{cases} ICT = \alpha S + \rho WTIC + \beta_1 URB + \beta_2 UNEM + \beta_3 TV + \beta_4 HSH_{15-40} + \beta_5 UNV + \varepsilon \\ \varepsilon \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the spatial autoregressive parameter measuring the spatial interaction intensity between a district and its neighboring districts and W represents the spatial weight matrix already defined above. Model (2) can alternatively be formulated as:

$$\begin{cases} ICT = (I - \rho W)^{-1}(\alpha S + \beta_1 URB + \beta_2 UNEM + \beta_3 TV + \beta_4 HSH_{15-40} + \beta_5 UNV) + (I - \rho W)^{-1} \varepsilon \\ \varepsilon \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

or,

$$\begin{cases} ICT = (I + \rho W + \rho^2 W^2 + \rho^3 W^3 + \rho^4 W^4 + \dots)(\alpha S + \beta_1 URB + \beta_2 UNEM + \beta_3 TV + \beta_4 HSH_{15-40} + \beta_5 UNV) + \\ (I + \rho W + \rho^2 W^2 + \rho^3 W^3 + \rho^4 W^4 + \dots) \varepsilon \\ \varepsilon \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

This expression implies that the ICT acquisition rate in a district is influenced not only by the values of the explanatory variables but also by those of all districts (whether neighboring or not) through the spatial transformation of the inverse matrix $(I - \rho W)$, revealing a "spatial multiplier effect" and by a "diffusion effect" where a shock that affects ICT acquisition rate in one district also affects rates in other districts. These impacts diminish with distance, contiguity order and the number of neighboring districts.

Table 5: Results of spatial model estimate

	INT	CP	MB
$\hat{\alpha}$	14.415 (0.091) *	9.014 (0.101)	30.144 (0.065) *
$\hat{\beta}_1$	0.199 (0.000) ***	0.157 (0.000) ***	0.108 (0.058) ***
$\hat{\beta}_2$	-0,652 (0.000) ***	-0,452 (0.024) **	-0,297 (0.071) *
$\hat{\beta}_3$	0.784 (0.025) **	0.671 (0.034) **	0.4440 (0.098) *
$\hat{\beta}_4$	0.654 (0.021) **	0.561 (0.010) ***	0.413 (0.083) *
$\hat{\beta}_5$	0.554 (0.005) ***	0.380 (0,009) ***	0,244 (0,043) **
ρ	0,352 (0,000) ***	0.261 (0.000) ***	0.280 (0.000) ***
R^2	0.752	0.777	0.743
LogL	-665.651	-441.1	-550.415
AIC	1329.3	900.2	1005.425
SC	1329.25	890.151	980.521
BP	311.092 (0.1346)	447.482 (0.065) *	222.092 (0.195)
LRT	10.744 (0.000) ***	9.975 (0.000) ***	7.7448 (0.000) ***

The results of estimating model (2) using the maximum likelihood method are detailed in table (5). We first note that the spatial parameter is positively significant: $\rho= 0.352$ for the Internet, 0.261 for the computer, and 0.28 for the mobile phone, with highly significant critical probabilities, as confirmed by the likelihood ratio test (LRT). So, the ICT acquisition rate in one district

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cannot be considered independent of the rate of nearby districts. This spatial externalities will impact the coefficients associated with the different determinants ICT rates: it is the spatial multiplier effects that accentuate the impact of variations in exogenous variables on the ITC rates. This indicates that the increase in ICT acquisition rates in Tunisian districts occurs through contagion and decisions to adopt such technologies may arise from imitating choices in the household's social environment. Essentially, acquiring a computer or mobile phone may not only depend on the services' utility but also on decisions made in the household's local area, like services with network externalities where satisfaction increases with more users (Diagne and Ly, 2009). All previous explanations show that the spatial organization of the Tunisian districts is an important explanatory component of ICT rate value and this point cannot be ignored.

On the other hand, it seems that the five socio-economic variables selected significantly explain the rate of ICT acquisition in Tunisian districts. The results indicate a strong positive correlation between the rate of ICT acquisition and the urban character, particularly for the Internet: the parameter β_1 is significantly positive. Indeed, rural areas in Tunisia still face challenges in accessing ICT infrastructure, primarily due to population density. The urbanization rate in 2014 was approximately 70%, compared to 53% in 2004, with urban development concentrated mainly in the eastern coastal strip. This concentration, between the regions of Tunis and Gabès via Sfax (coastal governorates), which have the largest infrastructures, facilitates ICT acquisition. This link generally confirms the growth process of human capital and productive capacity that may have occurred and the dynamic externalities that characterize urban regions in this context (Gagliardi and Per-coco, 2011). Disparities are more pronounced in less developed regions, where telecommunications infrastructure remains deficient. In this sense, urban districts with advantages like economic activities, universities and large administrative structures are better positioned to adopt these technologies. To mitigate urban congestion, cities must provide benefits to their inhabitants, such as agglomeration economies, which can impact technological development and consumption opportunities (Steven and al., 2015). This observation aligns with the agglomeration paradox, where low population density discourages investments perceived as unprofitable in such areas (Poncet and Ripert, 2004). Companies seeking network effects prefer larger cities for their comparative advantages, hindering the spread of new technologies.

Household income is a crucial factor in the adoption and use of ICTs. High-income households are more likely to have access to new technologies. The acquisition of the Internet, computers and mobile phone is influenced by the unemployment rate (β_2 is negatively significant). The cost of equipment, particularly computers, is notably high relative to the average income of households. Conversely, the affordability of mobile phones has improved following the sector's liberalization. At the regional level, the unemployment rate appears high in the districts of the center-west. The highest values are recorded in the governorates of Kef, Gafsa, and Sidi Bouzid, while the lowest rates are recorded in coastal areas, like Nabeul, Sfax and Monastir.

Household television ownership rate is positively linked to ICT adoption. TV access can indicate potential ICTs acquisition. The government demonstrates its ICT commitment through TV awareness programs, aligning with international ICT conferences. Note that, the significance of parameter β_3 appears more pronounced for the Internet compared to computers and mobile phones, underscoring television's importance as a knowledge source, especially in rural areas.

Age is a significant factor in the digital divide among individuals. Those aged 15 to 40 are more skilled in using new technologies for communication and learning: β_4 positively significant. Indeed, despite the growing number of connections and access opportunities continues to grow, young individuals are seen as the most active users of ICTs. While older individuals tend to be hesitant towards new technology and changes, the younger generation is keen on adopting the latest technological advancements (Chin and Fairlie, 2004). Referred to as the "Internet generation" or "digital natives", these young individuals exhibit diverse electronic communication and information practices based on their specific requirements (Blaya, 2013). They are highly curious about all aspects of this new technological environment. Recognizing the Internet's significant potential as a tool for work, they primarily use it for entertainment. Young people consider home connectivity advantageous for their studies, enabling access to valuable information resources for homework purposes (Cefrio, 2011, Poellhuber and al., 2012). Moreover, ICTs have swiftly evolved into a multifaceted instrument in the possession of young individuals, transcending traditional public affairs management. The influence of young people, with their numerical strength and visions for future societies, can fundamentally transform the world in the long run. Seeking avenues to fulfill their needs and aspirations, they find ICTs to be instrumental in achieving this objective. Lastly, young individuals, constituting a significant portion of the population, are enthusiastic technology users who adeptly adapt to technological advancements, making them an important market for the tech industry and contributing to the widespread adoption of ICTs (Ben Attar and Campbell, 2012).

Education level is a crucial factor in ICT adoption, a well-documented reality in economic literature highlighting the synergy between technology and human capital. Results indicate that the schooling rate positively influences the adoption and the use of ICTs within households, showing significant impact (β_5 positively significant). When children attend school, parents are encouraged to provide them with necessary tools for academic, communication and leisure purposes. Universities have consistently led the way in integrating and adoption of ICTs. Individuals with higher qualifications, who have been exposed to Internet or computers during their education, possess the necessary skills and competencies for utilizing these tools compared to those with lower levels of education. Tunisia has implemented diverse strategies to integrate ICTs in higher education through

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educational system reforms (ICT sectors, virtual University of Tunis, etc.), enabling academic institutions to become significant users of these new technologies (Walha and Peters, 2010). These findings align with several studies demonstrating the synergy between technology and human capital and that ICT user, especially those using computers, to have specific skills and qualifications to fully leverage the benefits offered by these technologies. Consequently, students are more inclined to use computers and mobile devices compared to individuals with varying levels of education. The disparity in ICT usage based on educational levels also reflects a gap influenced by the household's educational background. Research indicates that households with less educated levels tend to have lower ICT penetration (Diagne and Ly, 2009). However, it is important to interpret such findings carefully, as the high concentration of students in urban areas is largely driven by the clustering of universities and training centers in these regions. Higher education equips young adults with theoretical knowledge, practical technical skills and prepares them for the professional world. Nevertheless, certain essential skills in contemporary society, like "Soft Skills", are often not integrated into higher education curricula.

5. CONCLUSION

The descriptive analysis revealed significant regional disparities in ICT adoption rates across Tunisian districts. Thus, using exploratory spatial data analysis, a robust spatial autocorrelation was highlighted at global and local scales, detecting two clusters with a distinct "gap" between inland and coastal districts. Indeed, the spatial organization of Tunisian rural and urban spaces is an important explanatory component of the diffusion of ICTs. Neighborhood variables in particular are marked by significant spatial dependency patterns and different morphologies. Thus, districts cannot be considered as isolated spaces and on the contrary they overlap. Overall, the findings suggest that ICT adoption rates in Tunisian districts exhibit non-neutral spatial distribution patterns. These spillovers impact the diffusion of ICTs in the districts and make it possible to approximate the neighborhood effects, which are significantly associated with the characteristics of the territories. The socioeconomic dimension of the neighborhood effects, in connection with the phenomena of segregation and the policies of the districts in the light of diversity, is mainly highlighted in this study. Socio-economic, cultural and geographical factors appear to directly influence the adoption of ICTs in Tunisian districts. In this sense, a spatial autoregressive model (SAR) was developed, exploring the digital process dynamics and identifying potential interdependencies among districts. These results go beyond basic descriptive and static cartographic analyses, providing insights into the complexities of ICTs diffusion dynamics.

With the results of the next population census, this work could be the prelude to a dynamic analysis of ICTs and their regional disparities in Tunisia, under the impact of the push for education and the development of new means of information and communication since 2014.

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APPENDIX

Map of Tunisian governorates

